

Heterocyclic Compounds from Some Chlorodinitrobenzoic Acids

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Acridone was first prepared by Graebe and Lagodzinski¹ by cyclisation of *N*-phenylanthranilic acid in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid. Phosphorus pentachloride or thionyl chloride has also been used for this cyclisation².

Ordinarily *N*-phenylanthranilic acids cannot be easily obtained from substituted anthranilic acids; but when an *o*-chloronitrobenzoic acid having a reactive chlorine atom is allowed to react with substituted anilines, substituted *N*-phenylanthranilic acids³ are formed. These are then cyclised to the corresponding acridones in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc.).

During the present investigation a few acridones have been synthesised by condensing methyl 2-chloro-3, 5-dinitrobenzoate with some substituted anilines and subsequently cyclising the condensation products in presence of H₂SO₄ (Tables I and II).

With *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitroanilines, the *N*-phenylanthranilate derivatives could not, however, be cyclised to acridone derivatives under the conditions.

Methyl N-2'-Chlorophenyl-3, 5-dinitroanthranilate.—A mixture of methyl 2-chloro-3,5-dinitrobenzoate (1 g.), *o*-chloroaniline (0.6 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (1.5 g.), and dry methanol (25 ml) was refluxed for half an hour on a water bath. On cooling and diluting with water, the precipitate was crystallised from methanol in shining, light orange crystals (1.03 g.), m.p. 178°. (Found: Cl, 10.22. C₁₄H₁₀O₆N₂Cl requires Cl, 10.09%).

Following the above procedure, methyl 2-chloro-3,5-dinitrobenzoate was condensed with a few anilines to furnish *N*-arylanthranilates (Table I).

4-Chloro-5,7-dinitroacridone.—The preceding dinitroanthranilate (2 g.) was heated with 95% H₂SO₄ (14 g.) for half an hour on a water bath. The product was then cooled and poured on ice. The crude acridone separating was boiled successively with water, dilute sodium carbonate, and water. The product crystallised from acetic acid, furnishing 4-chloro-5,7-dinitroacridone (1.37 g.) as yellowish grey crystals, m.p. 345°. (Found: Cl, 11.21. C₁₃H₈O₆N₂Cl requires Cl, 11.11%).

1. *Annalen*, 1893, 276, 46; *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 1734.

2. Schroeter and Eisteb, *Annalen*, 1909, 267, 144.

3. Ullmann, *ibid.*, 1902, 268, 96; Furgotti and Lumine, *Gazzetta*, 1902, 33, 329; *Sen*, this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 53.

TABLE I

Methyl N-arylanthranilate.

S.No.	Amine used	Anthranilate formed.	Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula	Found	Reqd.
1	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	$R_1 = R_2 = H; R_3 = Cl$	85%	Lemon-yellow	162°	$C_{14}H_{10}O_2N_2Cl$	Cl : 9.91%	10.00%
2	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	$R_1 = R_2 = H; R_3 = Me$	75	"	150°	$C_{13}H_{11}O_2N_2$	N : 12.41	12.69
3	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	$R_1 = R_2 = H; R_3 = Me$	78	Yellow	185°	$C_{13}H_{11}O_2N_2$	N : 12.53	12.69
4	<i>p</i> -Aniline	$R_1 = R_2 = H; R_3 = OMe$	80	Yellowish orange	151°	$C_{13}H_{11}O_2N_2$	N : 12.27	12.10
5	α -Naphthylamine	$R_1 = H; R_2 = \left. \begin{array}{l} -CH=CH \\ R_1 \end{array} \right\}$ $-CH=CH$	76	Pale yellow	187°	$C_{16}H_{13}O_2N_2$	N : 11.66	11.44
6	β -Naphthylamine	$R_1 = H; R_2 = \left. \begin{array}{l} -CH=CH \\ R_2 \end{array} \right\}$ $-CH=CH$	75	Yellowish orange	197°	$C_{16}H_{13}O_2N_2$	N : 11.59	11.44
7	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	$R_1 = R_2 = H; R_3 = NO_2$	62	Pale yellow	178°	$C_{14}H_{10}O_2N_4$	N : 16.63	15.47
8	<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	$R_1 = R_2 = H; R_3 = NO_2$	68	Deep yellow	184°	$C_{14}H_{10}O_2N_4$	N : 15.31	15.47
9	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	$R_1 = R_2 = H; R_3 = NO_2$	70	Yellow	189°	$C_{14}H_{10}O_2N_4$	N : 15.34	15.47

Following the above procedure *N*-arylanthranilates (Table I, No. 1-6) were converted into the corresponding acridones (Table II).

TABLE II

Acridones.

Anthranilate used.*	5,7-Dinitro-acridone formed.	Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	2-Chloro-	75%	Grey	350°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl: 10.89%	11.11%
2	4-Methyl-	45	Brown	248°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂	N: 14.16	14.05
3	2-Methyl-	70	Grey	330°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂	N: 14.21	14.05
4	2-Methoxy-	65	Light red	268°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ N ₂	N: 13.58	13.33
5	3,4-Benz-	85	Light brown	333°	C ₁₇ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂	N: 11.22	11.38
6	1,2-Benz-	70	Yellowish brown	268°	C ₁₇ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂	N: 11.51	11.38

*Number, same as in Table I

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